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Apparel Tailoring Skill Improvement through Cooperative Learning and Action Research Methods

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Abstract

Currently, an integrated train station is under construction in Manggarai, thus resulting several teenagers had to drop out of school due to land acquisition. This community service activity provides skill training and socialization for the drop-out teenager in the age of 16 – 21 years old in South Manggarai to make apparels. This service, as a part of Tri Dharma activity from Universitas Negeri Jakarta, is the right activity to provide them with some skills and expertise. The strategy to socialize and equip them with skills was cooperative learning, in group work and assignment on how to make simple shirts in Shibori tie-dye pattern. The learning process was conducted with action research of John Elliot's model by going through 3 (three) learning stages on 20 participants. On the first stage implementation result, a number of 4 participants from Shibori tie-dye competent group got 88 or excellent, a number of 3 participants from making apparel pattern group got 8a or satisfactory, a number of 4 participants from basic tailoring group got 85 or good. On the second stage implementation, there were only 2 participants who received a good assessment for tailoring simple woman apparel. Then, on the third stage, a number of 2 participants from tailoring woman apparel group got 85 or good.

Key Words: Action Research, Cooperative Learning, Apparel Tailoring

Introduction

The construction of an integrated train station in DKI Jakarta forced the citizen who lived in Manggarai moved to an adequate living area. The massive number of temporary house surrounding Manggarai river is not endearing to see as the residents are mostly unemployed, do not have proper education, and are far from sufficient financial income to live in DKI Jakarta. Therefore, TriDharma of Universitas Negeri Jakarta, along with Research Institutions for Community Service, provides socialization and skills training to tailor apparel with Shibori tie-dye techniques.

The number of drop-out students in Manggarai area is the population of making apparel skill training with Shibori tie-dye prints. This activity will bring many benefits for them in their new living place. Apparel tailoring skill and making Shibori tie-dye prints can be implemented as an entrepreneurial asset or competence for working in boutique, convection or garment manufacture.

Methods

The method applied in this community service was qualitative descriptive with action research method of John Elliot model which implementing 3 stages. The flow of this method is as follows:

Action Research Chart of John Elliot Model

Discussion

Below are the photos of the community service activities.

Image of socialization session

Image of tie-dye shibori group

Image of a group making apparel patterns

Image of a group tailoring apparel

Image of the end-product

STAGE 1

20 participants, tie-dye shibori, making apparel pattern, tailoring apparel

Evaluation

STAGE 2

3 participants are competent in patterning
 4 participants are competent in tailoring,
 4 participants are competent in tie-dyeing

Evaluation

STAGE 3

2 participants are competent in apparel tailoring

The chart of action research activity

The result of apparel production attempt with R&D John Elliot method, with cooperative learning which was conducted through 3 stages, showed that the participants' competence suits to their talent and interest, On the first stage, all 20 participants were given the same instructions which were to do tie-dye, make pattern and give simple tailor training. On the evaluation of stage, their competence score was obtained. The score showed that 4 participants were competent in tie-dye, 3 participants were competent in the pattern, and 4 participants were

competent in the tailor of simple apparel model. The evaluation of stage 2 was carried out to give more complex tailoring skills. The evaluation result of stage 3 suggested that only 2 participants were competent in tailor with a good score.

Cooperative means to work collectively to achieve shared goals. In cooperative learning activity, students were demanded to individually aim for results which benefit every member of the group.

Below is the table of Students' Competence Score.

No	Name of Participant	Stage 1			Stage 2	Stage 3
		Tie Dye	Pattern	Tailor	Tailor	Tailor
1	Titi Ismanto	70	70	70	-	-
2	Anita	88	70	70	-	-
3	Conny	70	70	70	-	-
4	Erlina	70	70	70	-	-
5	Hanafi	70	82	85	85	competent
6	Farida	88	70	70	-	-
7	Siti Aodah	70	70	80	70	-
8	Nur Zairon	88	70	70	-	-
9	Yenny	70	70	70	-	-
10	Cholida	70	70	80	70	-
11	Eta Kelabora	70	70	70	-	-
12	Herwis	70	70	70	-	-
13	Ellen Tobing	85	70	70	-	-
14	Handini	70	70	70	-	-
15	Titin Indrawati	70	80	70	-	-
16	Ade yacob	70	83	85	85	competent
17	Teti S	70	70	70	-	-
18	Giman	70	70	70	-	-
19	Fatima	70	70	70	-	-
20	Fatida	70	70	70	-	-

Table. Steps of *Cooperative Learning*

Steps	Indicators	Teacher's Roles
Step 1	Share learning objectives and motivate participants	Facilitator shared the learning objectives, informed the target competences, and motivated the participants
Step 2	Present the lessons	Facilitator gave lessons to the participants
Step 3	Make the participants into groups	Facilitator instructed the participants to work in a group
Step 4	Assist the group work	Facilitators gave motivation and assistance to the participants who already worked in a big-sized group
Step 5	Evaluate	Facilitator evaluated the learning results of the lessons participants had participated in.
Step 6	Give rewards.	Facilitator rewarded the participants for their achievement in individual and group work.

A learning program is said to employ cooperative approach if, during the learning activity, students participate and work in a small group. What distinguishes cooperative learning from a mere group learning is that during the cooperative learning process, teachers act more like facilitators who assist students in acquiring a better understanding.

This corresponds with Johnson's cooperative learning theory saying that "Cooperative Learning is the incorporation of small group work into learning activity that allows students to work cooperatively to amplify their learning and another member's in the group." Also, as Slavian suggested, "Cooperative Learning is a learning model in which students study and work collaboratively in small groups of 4 to 6 person, with heterogeneous group composition. Learning cooperatively may help students in defining motivation and organization structure to establish a partnership. Based on cooperative learning theories and action research implementation, this community service program can be said successful.

Conclusion

The strategy of this community service program in providing socialization and skill training to tailor apparel which employed cooperative learning with John Elliot action research model method that conducted the 3 (three) learning stages on the 20 participants showed some results. On stage 1, 4 participants from the competent tie dye shibori group obtained 88 or excellent, 3 participants from making apparel pattern group obtained 8a or satisfactory, and 4 participants from basic tailoring group got or good. A number of 4 participants from basic tailoring group got 85 or good. On the second stage implementation, there were only 2 participants who received a good assessment for tailoring simple woman apparel. Then, on the third stage, a number of 2 participants from tailoring woman apparel group got 85 or good.

Reference

- Bunka Fashion College. (2009). *Blouses & Dresses*. Tokyo: Bunka Publishing Bureau
- Bunka Fashion College. (2009). *Fundamentals of Garment Design*. Tokyo: Bunka Publishing Bureau
- Bunka Fashion College. (2009). *Skirts & Pants*. Tokyo: Bunka Publishing Bureau
- Bray, Natalie. (1961). *Dress Pattern Designing: The Basic Principles of Cut and Fit*. London: Blackwell Science Ltd
- Dewi Suliyanthini, dkk. Industri creative, Soekarno Presindo, Semarang 2018.
- Emzir, Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan Kuantitatif & Kualitatif, Rajawali Press. PT RajaGrafindo Persada. Jakarta 2008.
- Hasanudin, M.Sn. Drs. 2001. *Batik Pesisiran: Melacak Pengaruh Etos Dagang Santripada Ragam Hias Batik*. Bandung: PT. Kiblat Buku Utama.
- Rukaesih, Ucu Cahyana. Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan. Rajawali Press. PT RajaGrafindo Persada. Jakarta 2015.
- Sugiono. Metoda Penelitian & Pengembangan Research and Development. Penerbit Alfabeta Bandung. 2015
- Van Der Hoop. 1914. *Indonesische Siermotieven*. Koninklijk Bataviasch Genootschap Van Kunsten en Wetenschappen.